

Assessing bibliodiversity through reference lists: A text analysis approach

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The presence or absence of publishers in large bibliographic databases highlights tangible and symbolic differences between small and large publishers, underlining their diverging incentive structures. To assess these differences, this contribution explores reference data from small (open access) publishers' journals in the Web of Science and Scopus. The analysis focuses on references that are not indexed in these databases and examines them from a text-as-data approach. The study frames two dimensions of relevance – visibility and impact – as proxies for assessing the scholarly bibliodiversity represented by small (open access) publishers' journals. Overall, the analysis identifies regional and linguistic specificities in the cited references and some observable thematic differences compared to articles from larger publishers. In particular, it can be argued that the visibility and impact of small (open access) publishers' publications is rather limited in these databases, thus hindering a broader bibliodiversity in the publishing landscape.

1. Introduction

The academic publication landscape is characterised by underlying tensions surrounding visibility and relevance. The tensions are themselves determined by diverging incentives within the science system. These incentives, for instance, underscore the divide between the academic and the policy dimensions. On one hand, there is the political push for open access (OA) publishing and its funding by institutions and funding agencies who are incentivised to facilitate knowledge transfer and transparency in the use of public funds. Herein lie externalised commercial incentives for publishers to further deepen the market for OA options. However, on the other hand, the systemic pressure to engage in academic discussions (through publications) means scholars often prioritise their productivity and the prestige of the publishing venue, regardless of its stance on OA. Academic practices from multiple levels compound these tensions. Consequently, for some journals, the question of OA is often of secondary importance, as rather a productive relation with their specific scientific community is their main concern (cfr. Knöchelmann, 2023; Leonelli et al., 2015; Severin et al., 2020; Tenopir et al., 2016). Further, smaller publishers have different incentives and structural conditions, such as financial and technological resources, than larger, commercial publishers (e.g., Butler et al., 2023). These differences co-determine whether smaller, OA journals can achieve the necessary quantitative and qualitative standards for indexation in large bibliographic databases (e.g., Web of Science [WoS] or Scopus) and to support a comprehensive transition to OA. These dynamics can aggregate into a vicious cycle,

highlighting a lack of structural resources to promote and increase visibility of smaller publications (i.e., bibliodiversity).

Within the OA transformation, diversity can be linked with visibility and impact, which in the face of an oligopolist business model becomes an overlooked dimension of the academic landscape. As the Jussieu Call for Open Science and Bibliodiversity states, OA must be complemented by “support for the diversity of those acting in scientific publishing (...) putting an end to the dominance of a small number among us imposing their terms to scientific communities” (*Jussieu Call for Open Science and Bibliodiversity*, 2017). We share this conceptual bibliodiversity approach.

In this contribution, we highlight disciplinary differences at the intersection of OA and publishers’ size to question the (biblio)diversity of the publication landscape (e.g., Estelle, 2021; Kaier & Lackner, 2019; Matthias et al., 2019). The study focuses on highly cited, OA literature and its references, assessing if and how these articles contribute to diversifying the publishing landscape (see Hawthorne, 2014). Methodologically, the study offers an exploratory text-as-data analysis based on natural language processing methods. Hence, the questions at the centre of the study are a) *whether small publishers’ journals contribute to the diversity of the (OA) publishing landscape* and, b) *if small publishers play a role within specific academic narratives?* In this sense, visibility (indexation in the bibliographic databases) will be taken as a characteristic of the relevance (impact) and diversity of the different academic discourses that coexist at various levels.

2. Methods and Data

We use bibliometric data from WoS and Scopus and centre on citation counts and reference lists. We narrow our scope to indexed and non-indexed references.¹ Additionally, we base our approach on a previous identification of small publishers from Crossref data,² as Crossref’s growth in membership primarily in the lower fee tiers indicates it likely contains many small publishers (Crossref, 2019, p. 7). Stephen and Stahlschmidt (2022) identified small publishers as those with 10 or fewer journals with 240 or fewer articles per year, or 1 journal with up to 102 articles per year. This dataset of small publishers consisted of 23,058 journals published by 14,328 publishers.

We matched this dataset using ISSN identifiers to the Competence Network for Bibliometrics’ in-house versions of the WoS and Scopus databases.³ We filtered the matches to *articles* and *reviews* published in *peer-reviewed journals* between 2014 and 2021, from which we then differentiated non-small (large) publishers. We examine articles and reviews as they carry the largest share of original academic contributions and, hence, the largest share of citations (see Donthu et al., 2021; Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015). Items were classified into six fields of science (FoS) based on disciplinary metadata from WoS and Scopus and matched to the Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development’s (OECD) FOS classification.⁴ Using WoS and Scopus item metadata on OA status, we classify journals and publishers as OA or non-OA. We group items by journals and then by publishers, setting a threshold at 90%: any yearly output (per journal per publisher) with at least 90% of its published items in OA format is considered

¹ Indexed references are the *cited items* recorded in the same database as the *citing item*.

² The identification of small publishers was commissioned by the Knowledge Exchange (KE) consortium. Thus, the final sample in Stephen and Stahlschmidt (2022) includes only journals from KE countries.

³ We make use of the April 2022 snapshots (<https://bibliometrie.info/>).

⁴ Agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, humanities, medical and health sciences, natural sciences, and social sciences. See (OECD, 2007) for further details.

OA – otherwise, it is non-OA. The distinction between OA types was subsumed into this broad classification, since the interest lies at the distinction of open and non-open items, regardless of the licensing format used.

We used citation counts for a three-year period after publication to calculate an indicator for highly cited (HC) items, indicating whether publications were in the top 10% most cited publications of their field and publication year (Donthu et al., 2021). We use a three-year window for HC as published scientific works tend to reach a stable level of citations indicative of long-term impact three years after publication (Hyland & Jiang, 2017; Moed, 2005). As we explore the intersection of small HC-OA literature, we narrowed our sample to HC publications from small OA publishers. We focus on the small OA-HC subsample as it carries the most visibility and relevance (citation counts), characterising the state of research in each field. Further, we distinguish between the common items in both databases and the items unique to each database to highlight the varying visibility of journals across bibliometric databases.

The overall data sample consists of 11,018,859 (9,743,423) articles and reviews from 33,196 (22,424) journals, published by 8,320 (12,823) publishers found both in WoS and Scopus (exclusive items –*found only in one, but not the other database*– in parentheses). Details of the number of items, journals, and publishers in each database by OA type and size are shown in Table 1. Table 2 summarises the total, unique, and (non)-indexed references counts in HC items from small OA publishers in WoS and Scopus. Due to the non-systematic classification in disciplines and years in the sub-sample’s composition, the share of small OA publishers’ items that are HC-OA does not equal 10%.

Figure 1 summarises the methodological decisions in the form of a flow chart. The diagram visualises the data selection, filtering and, wrangling processes. All analyses were carried out in R; data-wrangling with *dplyr* and *stringr* (Wickham, 2023; Wickham et al., 2023), text analysis *tm* and *stopwords* (Feinerer et al., 2023; Muhr et al., 2022), *igraph* (Csárdi et al., 2024), *entity* (Rinker, 2023), and *cld2* (Sites, 2013) packages, whilst visualisations with *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016).

Figure 1. Methodological Flow Chart for Bibliometric Data

Table 1. Item, Journal and Publisher Counts in WoS and Scopus, by Size and Access Type*

Database	Common Items (Unique Items)	Journals	Publishers	%
All				
Total	11,018,859 (9,743,423)	33,196 (22,242)	8,320 (12,823)	100.0
WoS	(3,023,805)	(2,872)	(3,077)	31.0
Scopus	(6,719,618)	(19,370)	(9,746)	69.0
Open Access Publishers				
Total	630,859 (525,813)	4,305 (6,256)	1,984 (3,414)	100.0
WoS	(75,689)	(907)	(771)	14.4
Scopus	(450,124)	(5,349)	(2,643)	85.6
Non-Open Access Publishers				
Total	10,388,000 (9,217,610)	28,891 (15,986)	11,439 (9,409)	100.0
WoS	(2,948,116)	(1,965)	(2,306)	32.1
Scopus	(6,269,494)	(14,021)	(7,103)	67.9
Large Open Access Publishers				
Total	593,540 (473,750)	3,905 (5,856)	1,472 (2,355)	100.0
WoS	(69,843)	(787)	(564)	14.7
Scopus	(403,907)	(4,555)	(1,791)	85.3
Small Open Access Publishers				
Total	37,319 (52,063)	400 (914)	512 (1,059)	100.0
WoS	(5,846)	(120)	(207)	11.1
Scopus	(46,217)	(794)	(852)	88.9
Large Non-Open Access Publishers				
Total	10,204,703 (8,841,100)	27,756 (14,025)	9,743 (6,459)	100.0
WoS	(2,883,883)	(1,786)	(1,637)	32.6
Scopus	(5,957,217)	(12,239)	(4,822)	67.4
Small Non-Open Access Publishers				
Total	183,297 (376,510)	1,135 (1,961)	1,696 (2,950)	100.0
WoS	(64,233)	(179)	(669)	17.0
Scopus	(312,277)	(1,782)	(2,281)	83.0

Note: *The size classification is applied at the publisher level, hence, journals and items classified as small belong to the publishers classified as such. OA Publishers (small and large) refer to publishers within our 90% threshold. Percentages for each database are calculated regarding the total number of unique items per category (values in parentheses).

Table 2. Reference Description of HC Small OA Publications

	WoS	%	Scopus	%	Total	%
HC Items^a	415	-	1,491	-	2,533	-
Total References	13,463	-	71,052	-	143,674	-
Unique References	13,369	100	66,744	100	127,209	100
Indexed References	3,547	26.5	44,839	67.2	97,942	77.0
Non-Indexed References	9,822	73.5	21,905	32.8	29,267	23.0

Note: a: Items are identified based on a three-year citation window (HC3).

3. Results

3.1 Assessing Bibliodiversity

Figure 2 shows, for each field, the five most frequent sources of references not indexed in WoS and Scopus that were cited by HC items from small OA publishers. The sources are also disaggregated by HC items indexed in both databases (common) or unique to one database. These results show that non-peer-reviewed materials represent relevant document types (e.g., various preprint, theses, and even digital material) and non-article documents in journals such as Nature and Science. Similarly, the presence of journals and sources in languages other than English supports the notion that small publishers promote (at least one of the dimensions of) (biblio-)diversity via non-mainstream sources in HC articles. However, the extent to which said diversity is tangibly transmitted into the narratives and discourses is unclear, as the share of these sources is rather small (see Table 2 for the count of HC items and Table 3 for the listing of languages identified in reference lists).

Figure 2. Top Five Non-Indexed Reference Sources by FOS in Common and Unique Items in WoS and Scopus

Table 3 addresses language diversity for *cited* items. The numbers tally the languages of cited items' titles. Following our bibliodiversity argument, it is important to note this variety, as it may indicate “the preservation of national languages in scholarly communication” (Giménez Toledo et al., 2019). Yet, English remains the dominant language in both levels of analysis (indexed and non-indexed references). The dominant Anglophone trend is expected for indexed sources, as these represent the international standard of scientific practices, i.e., an academic *lingua franca*. Notably, the counts for languages other than English increase in non-indexed sources. The variety of languages also illustrates the representation of specific regional academic communities. A linguistic variety of cited items is also indicative of a process of transmission, by which local knowledge is carried into the mainstream (English-speaking) scholarship.

Table 3. Languages in Indexed and Non-Indexed References of Common and Unique HC-OA Items in WoS and Scopus

Indexed References			Non-Indexed References		
Languages	n	Database	Languages	n	Database
Common Items					
English	19,594	Scopus	English	12,335	Scopus
Spanish	147		Spanish	482	
Chinese	12		French	279	
Polish	9		German	186	
French	5		Galician	69	
English	4,713	WoS	English	4,174	WoS
Spanish	15		French	232	
French	11		German	184	
Lithuanian	6		Spanish	178	
Czech	4		Italian	70	
Unique Items					
English	10,996	Scopus	English	9,711	Scopus
Russian	159		Spanish	282	
Spanish	50		German	273	
Slovenian	19		Croatian	263	
Chinese	19		French	193	
English	1,257	WoS	English	1,800	WoS
Russian	10		Spanish	175	
Spanish	5		French	141	
Lithuanian	2		German	87	
Czech	2		Italian	59	

3.2. Text Analysis Approach

Now, considering the natural language dimension, the approach is set on textual structures; we present an overview of the specific dimensions of textual relevance (visibility and impact): a) term frequencies, b) term frequency network, and c) entity recognition. We explore the latent thematic connections in journal and item titles that are indicative of closeness and similarity in field-specific work and linguistic and territorial dimensions. These approximations shed light on different characteristics of appearance, relevance, and relation. Hence, each of the dimensions contributes to the characterisation of references (and epistemic) practices in HC-OA literature. Thus, these elements are a more direct connection to the diverse structure of knowledge (re-)production.

3.3. Term Frequency

Term frequencies are counts of the most frequently used words in a text string. In this case, we use the citing items' titles as the text string and, after removing stop words, decomposed the strings into words, or tokens, and divided the sum of these tokens by the total number of tokens (i.e., for $t_l = n_{t_l}/N_m$, where n is the sum for t_l and N is the sum of all terms – $t_1 \dots t_n$). Figure 3, however, is ordered by the frequency of the least used words. The calculation groups all words that are sparsely used (e.g., specific discipline-based terms or concepts) and counts them, hence the large spike to the left. The long right-tailed distributions signal a) an agglomeration of very specific words in the items' titles, as well as b) a very large quantity of common fill words relating to methods or approaches, e.g., “review”, “model”, or “analysis”, as shown in Figure 4. The frequency of the very specific words is quite low, as shown by the spike to the right of 0. This behaviour can be indicative of similarity and overall uniformity in HC items from small OA publishers, since the distributions evidence a sparse disciplinarity and, within each field, potentially less interaction than expected. So, across disciplines, item titles are similarly structurally composed, and some degree of regularity exists regarding the use of words to describe the research. These words, moreover, are highly similar, while the topics they are applied to are extremely diverse.

Figure 3. Term Frequencies in Small OA Publishers' HC Item Titles, by FoS, Database, and Whether the Item is Common to Both Databases or Unique to One

3.4. Term Network in Journal and Reference Titles

Visually guiding our perspective, we estimate a term frequency – inverse document frequency (tf-idf) for both *citing* and *cited* items, and create a reference link between them, i.e., a network (Figure 4). We can observe directed relations between these terms (nodes – the bigger, the more

Table 4. Top Five Locations Identified in Journal and Item Titles (Small OA Journals, per Field in WoS and Scopus)

Location Entities (Journal Titles)	n	Location Entities (Item Titles)	n
<i>Agricultural Sciences</i>			
Europe	32	China	284
Pakistan	19	Australia	125
Japan	16	Europe	125
China	14	Brazil	108
India	13	Japan	108
<i>Engineering and Technology</i>			
Arctic	14	China	16
India	6	India	10
Germany	4	Europe	7
Spring	4	Australia	5
United States	4	Spain	5
<i>Humanities</i>			
Europe	59	Spain	52
Britain	30	Europe	45
India	29	Turkey	34
Cambridge	28	China	20
France	23	United States	20
<i>Medical and Health Sciences</i>			
England	137	United States	307
London	43	China	276
United States	28	England	140
Europe	20	Japan	139
United Kingdom	19	Europe	136
<i>Natural Sciences</i>			
London	114	China	1045
France	113	India	662
China	110	Brazil	632
Paris	100	Australia	479
Europe	96	Mexico	475
<i>Social Sciences</i>			
China	106	China	191
Europe	86	United States	113
Asia	61	Europe	107
Indonesia	59	India	104
Africa	45	Spain	99

4. Discussion

Our analyses evidenced that the share of small OA publications is notably slender in comparison to the overall sample. This attests to the incentives and challenges small publishers face regarding OA, evidenced in the very low item counts. However, there is potential for small OA scholarship. HC items show the extent to which small publishers can channel knowledge from specific research communities into the mainstream, and, within them, specific narratives and epistemic practices. We look beyond the mere citation data and highlight the role of referencing across disciplines. We understand the different referencing patterns as particular practices that, dependent on topics, regions, and languages, help shape epistemic narratives. Thus, the HC-OA items represent a relevant microcosm to make certain disciplinary differences evident, whilst highlighting them as core characteristics of epistemic practices. However, the diversity in this sub-sample indicates a trade-off between citation expectations and thematic diversity, as shown in the main terms used in titles.

For both dimensions of our analysis – visibility and impact – the use of non-indexed references appears as common practice beyond disciplinary boundaries. Top performing items (thus, highly visible) make constant use of other types of periodicals, preprints, and other non-indexed materials. This practice facilitates a better understanding of the epistemic composition of fields, communities, or even journals. Moreover, small OA publishers are greatly outweighed by their larger counterparts, not only in terms of visibility in the databases, but also in perceived impact – an underlying consequence of total output breadth. Thus, we observe a rather limited impact of small OA literature in the academic publishing landscape. Despite a linguistic representation and a diverse citation record, the extent to which these elements potentially move on to the mainstream discourses is limited, given the very small share of HC items. However, the mere presence of these journal provides a silver-lining of diversity and representation of different scholarly backgrounds.

5. Conclusion

We have shown that small publishers, through their direct contact with academic communities, can effectively amplify the diversity of the overall publishing landscape. Varied linguistic representations, as well as diverse geographical directions are indicative of a biblio-diverse landscape. Yet, the impact, in terms of the share of highly cited literature, represents a pitfall for the smaller OA publishers. Subsequently, the works published in the journals of smaller publishers do not reach the scale of more visible, large publishers' journals. Finally, we argue that bibliodiversity should be the focus of more studies of this kind, focusing on science communication, publishing models, and innovation possibilities that foster and deepen open science.

Open science practices

Data for this research was obtained through the institutional infrastructure of the Competence Network for Bibliometrics (KB) in Germany. Microdata is subject to licensing agreements between the KB and Elsevier (Scopus) and Clarivate (WoS), respectively. Processed data, replication codes, and aggregated lists will be shared upon request.

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Author contributions

Roberto Cruz Romero: Conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, methodology, visualisation, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

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Stephan Stahlschmidt: Conceptualisation, funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, writing – review and editing.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests.

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